

PARACHOR AND RING STRUCTURE. PART III

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Structure of diacetyl acetone and pyrone and its derivatives is considered on electronic basis. Parachor values contradict the view of Deshpande and co-workers and suggest that pyrone and diethyl pyrone have bridge ring structure, while dimethyl pyrone has simple ring structure. Structure of diacetyl acetone is similarly discussed.

Deshpande, Kaweeshwar and Bhagwat (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 155) have determined and calculated the parachor of diacetyl acetone in ethyl acetate assuming that the contribution is due to two rings of five. But as explained in Part II the contribution due to a third ring of six must be added. This makes the bridge ring value 334.1 and not 328, but fails to decide between open chain and closed chain bridge structure. The value 340.3 for closed chain enol form is equally far off from the observed value 324.

Electronic structure requires the existence of singlet linkages and semi-polar bond

The calculated value of parachor of the keto-form assuming three rings is 309.3 since each ringlet has parachor -12.4 . For enol ring the value is 315.6 as there is one semi-polar bond. The open chain value is equally nearer the observed value. Hence the parachor results support the view that diacetyl acetone is a tautomeric mixture of the two enolic forms.

In case of isonitrosocamphor Deshpande, Kaweeshwar and Bhagwat (*loc.cit.*) have given an incorrect value for its calculated parachor as 438. Actually this is 425.2 assuming only two rings of five. The observed value is 438, their conclusion therefore that the bridge ring in isonitrosocamphor corresponds to two rings of five is incorrect. When the structure is considered in space there is one more ring of six, which makes the parachor value 431.2. This is nearer the observed value than the value based on two rings.

Camphor also contains bridge ring, the values on the basis of two and three rings are 381.8 and 387.9 while the observed result is too low to justify any inference. Our results with the parachor of camphor in ethyl acetate are presented in Table I.

Deshpande, Dingankar and Kokil (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 592) have discussed the structure of pyrones and its derivatives which may have simple ring structure or bridge structure as suggested by Collie.

Deshapande, Kaweeswar and Bhagwat have determined the parachors of the above. The values are given in Table II.

TABLE I
 x = molar fraction of camphor.

Temp.	d of soln.	Surface tension.	P obs. in soln.	P camphor (obs.).	x .
20°	0.9272	25.85	254.1	364.2	0.257
30	0.9182	24.66	253.7	362.7	
40	0.9086	24.35	255.4	365.0	
20	0.9283	25.98	247.3	362	0.217
30	0.9189	24.10	246.4	359	
40	0.9057	23.45	247.4	361	
50	0.8995	22.54	246.8	359	
60	0.8892	21.74	247.4	361	
20	0.9328	26.39	266.3	364.9	0.338
30	0.9236	25.58	266.9	366	
40	0.9152	24.70	267.0	367	
50	0.9086	23.29	265.1	362	
60	0.8966	22.61	266.8	366	

TABLE II

Substance.	P (obs.).	P (calc.) simple ring.	P (calc.) bridge ring.
Pyrone	195	208.1	219
Dimethyl pyrone	309	286.1	297
Diethyl pyrone	355	364.1 (359)	375 (370)

Their calculated values for diethyl pyrone as 59.1 and 370 are corrected by us. From the results they conclude that diethyl pyrone and pyrone have simple ring structure while dimethyl pyrone has bridge ring structure, assuming that bridge ring consists of two rings. The values for Collie's structure for dimethyl pyrone and diethyl pyrone should therefore each be increased by 6.1 on the basis of three rings. However the conclusions remain unaffected.

Collie's formulae when considered from electronic stand point, reveals that pyrones contain only two double bonds and the third double bond is really a semi-polar bond.

The values obtained with these structures are as follows.

TABLE III

Substance.	P (obs.).	P (calc.) (2 rings of 5)	P (calc.) (3 rings)
Pyrone	195.0	194.2	200.3
Dimethyl pyrone	309	272.2	278.3
Diethyl pyrone	355	350.2	356.3

The consideration of 3 rings gives closer approximation with experimental values. Further the bridge ring formulae agree better, with the experimental results in case of pyrone and diethyl pyrone, while dimethyl pyrone gives better results with simple ring structure.